

HIGH TEMPERATURE TENSILE PROPERTIES OF IN SITU TiBw/Ti60 COMPOSITES WITH NOVEL NETWORK MICROSTRUCTURE

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Keywords: *Titanium matrix composites (TMCs); In situ; High temperature tensile properties; Network microstructure; Powder Metallurgy*

Abstract

TiB whiskers reinforced high temperature titanium Ti60 alloy (TiBw/Ti60) composites with a novel network microstructure have been successfully fabricated by the system of large spherical Ti60 powders and fine TiB₂ powders. The results show that TiB whiskers are in situ synthesized around large Ti60 matrix particles and then formed a novel three-dimensional (3D) network microstructure. The high temperature tensile strength can be improved by fabricating network structured composites. Moreover, the strength of the composites is increased with increasing the reinforcement volume fraction. The tensile strength of 8vol.%TiBw/Ti60 composites with a network microstructure is increased by 61.1%, 57.4% and 45.5% compared with that of the monolithic Ti60 alloy at 600°C, 700°C and 800°C, respectively. The superior improvement can be mainly attributed to the network microstructure, grain refinement and usage of large spherical Ti60 powders.

1. Introduction

In order to further enhance the mechanical properties of titanium based materials for some critical applications, much attention has been paid on titanium matrix composites (TMCs) due to its superior properties such as high specific strength, high specific stiffness at room temperature and high temperature properties [1, 2, 3]. In particular, discontinuously reinforced titanium matrix composites (DRTMCs), fabricated by *in situ* methods are sought-after due to their superior and isotropic properties along with low cost [4-7].

Improving the high temperature mechanical properties of DRTMCs is the critical problem. Traditionally, researchers have always been seeking better reinforcements, better matrix alloys, better fabrication methods and a more homogenous distribution of reinforcements to improve the performance of DRTMCs [8, 9]. It is unanimous that TiB whisker (TiBw) was regarded as the optimal reinforcement due to its high modulus and hardness and good chemical compatibility with Ti [1].

Ti-1100 (USA), IMI834 (UK), BT39 (Russian) and Ti60 (China) alloys possessing the highest service temperature of 600°C can be used as matrix to fabricate the highest temperature TMCs. As early as 1990s, high temperature titanium alloy Ti-1100 [10, 11] and IMI834 [12] are used to fabricate continuous SiC fiber reinforced titanium matrix composites. Recently, Xiao et al fabricated (TiBw+La₂O₃)/IMI834 composites [13] and (TiBw+TiCp+La₂O₃)/IMI834 composites [14] by melting technique, and obtained a superior high temperature creep resistance. Ti-1100 alloy was also selected to fabricate DRTMCs such as TiCp/Ti-1100 composites [15] and (TiBw+TiCp)/Ti-1100 composites [16]. By employing Ti6242 alloy, Lu et al [17] have successful prepared in situ (TiBw+TiCp)/Ti6242 composites by melting technique followed by forging processing, and the ultimate tensile strength was improved to 639MPa at 650°C. In addition, Liu et al [18, 19] fabricated 10vol.%TiCp/TA15 composites by laser melting deposition. The composites exhibited 625MPa, 476MPa and 342MPa at 600°C, 650°C and 700°C, respectively. However, there is no effort to fabricate high temperature titanium alloy matrix composites using Ti60 as matrix or using powder metallurgy (PM) process. Factually, the high temperature strength of Ti60 is further higher than that of Ti6242 alloy.

Additionally, powder metallurgy (PM) coupled with in situ reaction synthesis has been considered an effective method to fabricate DRTMCs, largely due to its ability for microstructure control, near net shape processing and minimal material waste [1]. However, DRTMCs fabricated by the conventional PM technique exhibit extreme brittleness and only a limited improvement in performance [1, 6]. It is worth mentioning that the bottleneck problem of brittleness of DRTMCs fabricated by conventional PM process was solved by tailoring a novel network microstructure in our previous work. A novel TiBw/Ti6Al4V composites fabricated by a simplified PM process (low energy milling and one-step sintering) exhibited superior combination of mechanical properties [4]. Moreover, the maximum service temperature of TiBw/Ti6Al4V composites was significantly increased by 150~200°C by tailoring the novel network microstructure on the basis of the same tensile strength [20]. However, due to the limitation of Ti6Al4V matrix alloy, the maximum service temperature of the novel composites is defined at 600°C.

Therefore, it is important, necessary and also interesting to design and fabricate novel TiBw/Ti60 composites with a novel network microstructure fabricated by the simplified PM process. This novel composite will exhibit the highest strength or strengthening effect at high temperatures due to the employment of the best TiBw reinforcement, the highest strength Ti60 alloy at high temperature, the

most effective fabrication method and the novel network microstructure.

2. Experimental procedures

In order to fabricate TiBw/Ti60 composite with a network microstructure, the large and spherical Ti60 powders with a particle size of 120-220 μm (Fig. 1 (a)), fine and prismatic TiB₂ powders with that of 1-8 μm (Fig. 1 (b)) were selected in the present study. The analyzed composition (in wt.%) of Ti60 alloy is 5.9 Al, 4.2Sn, 3.5Zr, 0.4Mo, 0.38Nb, 0.93Ta, 0.38Si, 0.04Fe, 0.06C, 0.01N, 0.003H, 0.07O, 0.3 others, and balance titanium. The selected two powders were low energy milled at 200rpm for 8h with a milled media to material ratio of 5:1 under an argon atmosphere. The aim of low-energy milling process was not to break down the large Ti60 powders but to make fine TiB₂ powders be tapped onto the surface of the large Ti60 particles. Then, the mixed powders were hot pressed in vacuum (10⁻² Pa) at 1300°C under a pressure of 20MPa for 60min. TiB whiskers were synthesized during the reaction hot pressing process between Ti and TiB₂ [1], and then 5vol.%, 8vol.% and 12vol.% TiBw/Ti60 composites with a network microstructure were fabricated according to the following reaction equation:

Fig. 1. SEM micrographs of raw materials: (a) Ti60 powders, (b) TiB₂ powders.

Tensile specimens have gauge dimensions of 15mm×5mm×2mm and a total of five samples were

tested for each composite. High temperature tensile tests were carried out in air using an Instron-1186

universal testing machine at 600°C, 700°C and 800°C, and a constant crosshead speed of 0.5 mm/min (corresponding strain rate is $5.5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$). Microstructure observation was performed using a scanning electron microscopy (SEM, Hitachi S-4700).

3. Results and Discussions

Fig. 2 shows SEM micrographs of the as-sintered 5 vol.% TiB whiskers (TiBw) reinforced Ti60 composites (TiBw/Ti60) with a novel network microstructure at different magnifications. It can be clearly seen that the *in situ* synthesized TiBw reinforcement is uniformly distributed around the large Ti60 matrix particles, and formed a three

dimensional (3D) network microstructure. The overall network unit, as shown in Fig. 2a, can be divided into a TiBw-rich network boundary region with a well defined boundary width and a TiBw-lean matrix region. As reported previously [4, 20], the TiBw-rich network boundary around the Titanium matrix particles is equal to grain boundary, which can constrain the primary β grain under 200 μm (the size of as-received Titanium particles) as shown in Fig. 1(a). This size ($\sim 200\mu\text{m}$) is much lower than that ($\sim 900\mu\text{m}$) of the as-sintered Ti60 alloy (Fig. 3a). Furthermore, TiBw can refine the $\alpha+\beta$ phases in the TiBw-lean region by acting as the nucleation site of α phase and stopping the growth of lamellar $\alpha+\beta$ phases [20].

Fig. 2. SEM micrographs of the as-sintered 5 vol.% TiBw/Ti60 composite with a network microstructure. The magnification increases from (a) to (c).

The network microstructure can play a superior strengthening effect by introducing TiBw reinforcement into the network boundary region,

which overcomes the drawback of grain boundary weakening effect at high temperatures observed in traditional engineering alloys. Additionally, the

matrix in the composite with a network microstructure exhibits platelet or equiaxed microstructure as shown in Fig. 2(b). The formation of the equiaxed microstructure is believed to be beneficial to the mechanical properties of the composite. Fig. 2(c) shows that TiB whiskers grew into the neighboring Ti60 particles like dowel connectors owing to its special B27 structure [1], resulting in a strong and gradient boundary connecting the neighboring Ti particles, which can be viewed as a reinforced grain boundary.

Fig. 3(a) shows the SEM micrograph of the as-sintered monolithic Ti60 alloy. It can be seen that the typical widmanstätten microstructure presenting large primary β grains and lamellar α phase is formed in the as-sintered Ti60 alloy. The size of the primary β grains is much larger ($\sim 900\mu\text{m}$) than that of the as-received Ti60 powders, which is harmful to

the mechanical property. For the $\alpha+\beta$ or near α two-phase Ti alloys, the formation of the widmanstätten lamellar microstructure is common after cooling from above the β transus temperature, which is believed to be harmful to the mechanical properties of titanium alloys [20]. The formation of much large primary β grains indicates that the loose Ti64 powders merged during hot-press sintering process, and subsequently the new primary β grains were formed from the merged β phase. However, the size of the primary β grains of the TiBw/Ti60 composites with a network microstructure is constrained to be similar with that ($\sim 200\mu\text{m}$) of the as-received Ti60 powders (Figs. 2 and 3), due to the existence of reinforcement with a network distribution. This is equal to refinements of the β grain and α phase, which are beneficial to the mechanical property.

Fig. 3. SEM micrographs of (a) the monolithic Ti60 alloy, (b) 8vol.% and (c) 12vol.%TiBw/Ti60 composites with a network microstructure.

For the 5vol.%TiBw/Ti60 composites, the microstructure is bi-continuous embodying

continuous matrix and quasi-continuous reinforcement, which is beneficial to the

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combination of mechanical properties. When the volume fraction is increased to 8vol.%, the microstructure becomes quasi-continuous matrix and continuous reinforcement as seen from Fig. 3(b). Moreover, self-jointing structures of TiB whiskers except for single whisker can be clearly observed. This is certainly positive to the strengthening effect of TiBw reinforcement. But, when the volume fraction to 12vol.%, the structure of continuous TiBw agglomeration and discrete matrix particles replaces the above bi-continuous structure, which is certainly harmful to the mechanical properties of the composites. The formation of TiBw agglomeration can be attributed to that Ti source for reaction synthesis is insufficient near local network boundary due to excessive TiB₂ addition.

Fig. 4 shows the high temperature tensile properties of the monolithic Ti60 alloy and the network structured 5vol.%, 8vol.% and 12vol.% TiBw/Ti60 composites. On the one hand, using Ti60 alloys as matrix can effectively increase the tensile strength at higher temperatures compared with the TiBw/Ti6Al4V composites [20]. On the other hand, the tensile strength at high temperature is further increased by using Ti60 alloy and network microstructure compared with the (TiBw+TiCp)/Ti6242 composites [17]. The tensile strength of the composites increases with increasing the TiBw volume fractions at high temperatures, while that of 12vol.% TiBw/Ti60 composites falls down due to the continuous TiBw agglomeration (Fig. 3(c)).

Fig. 4 Tensile properties of the monolithic Ti60 alloy and the network structured 5vol.%, 8vol.% and 12vol.% TiBw/Ti60 composites at (a) 600°C, (b) 700°C and (c) 800°C, respectively.

For the 5vol.%TiBw/Ti60 composites, the tensile strength is increased to 787MPa, 625MPa and 396MPa from 552MPa, 458MPa and 303MPa at 600°C, 700°C and 800°C, respectively. These are

equivalent with increases by 42.6%, 36.5% and 30.7%, respectively. Furthermore, the tensile strength of 8vol.%TiBw/Ti60 composites is increased to 889MPa, 721MPa and 453MPa,

respectively. That is to say, the tensile strength can be increased by 61.1%, 57.4% and 45.5% compared with that of the monolithic Ti60 alloy at 600°C, 700°C and 800°C, respectively. It is certain that the tensile strength of the composites decreases with increasing temperatures due to the matrix weakening. It is worth pointing out that the tensile strength of the composites can be certainly further increased by subsequent heat treatment according to the previous experience [21]. The superior improvement in high temperature strength can be interpreted as follows: TiB whiskers with dowel-like structure as ceramic reinforcement are introduced into the grain boundary (network boundary) and formed into the novel network microstructure. This can effectively decrease the grain boundary weakening effect at high temperatures. Moreover, the in situ synthesized TiBw can exhibit the effective grain boundary strengthening effect even at high temperatures. Particularly for the 8vol.%TiBw/Ti60 composites, the continuous TiBw network boundary can dominate the tensile behavior of the composites (Fig. 3(b)). Additionally, the refined grains with ceramic reinforced boundary are certainly positive to strengthen the composites at high temperatures. However, the 12vol.%TiBw/Ti60 composites just exhibit slight improvement even decrease in high temperature tensile strength due to the existence of TiBw agglomeration.

In addition, the tensile elongation of the composites decreases with increasing TiBw volume fractions and increases with increasing temperatures. It is worth pointing out that the tensile elongation of 5vol.%TiBw/Ti60 composites slightly decreases to 9.2%, 12.8% and 19.2% from 12%, 15.6% and 21.8% at 600°C, 700°C and 800°C, respectively. Even for the 8vol.%TiBw/Ti60 composites with a network microstructure, the elongation keeps 7.5%, 9.2% and 11.7%, which can be viewed as an noticeable improvement considering the 61.1%, 57.4% and 45.5% improvement in high temperature tensile strength.

In summary, the maximum service temperature of the TiBw/Ti60 composites can be increased while retaining the same strength of the monolithic Ti60 alloy, along with a suitable elongation. In addition, it is reasonable that both the strength and the elongation can be further increased by the subsequent deformation such as hot extrusion [22].

Fig. 5 shows the schematic illustration of TiBw/Ti60 composites with a novel network microstructure. As seen from Fig. 5, the TiB whiskers can effectively joint the adjacent Ti60 matrix particles like dowel

connectors. The addition of TiBw ceramic reinforcement in the boundary can effectively overcome the grain boundary weakening effect at high temperatures. Moreover, the TiB whiskers reinforcement, particularly for the self-jointing TiBw reinforcement can exhibit an effective grain boundary strengthening effect. In addition, the quasi-continuous TiBw network structure and the continuous TiBw network structure can inspire a superior strengthening effect by dominating the tensile behavior of the composites. It is important that the Ti60 alloy as matrix possessing high strength at high temperatures can support the strengthening effect of the network microstructure and TiBw reinforcement. In summary, the superior strengthening effect of TiBw/Ti60 composites with a network microstructure is described by the schematic illustration.

Fig. 5 Schematic illustration of TiBw/Ti60 composites with a novel network microstructure.

5. Summary

- (1) TiB whiskers reinforced high temperature titanium Ti60 alloy composites (TiBw/Ti60) with a network microstructure were successfully fabricated by reaction hot pressing and using the large spherical Ti60 powders and fine TiB₂ powders.
- (2) The tensile strength of 8vol.%TiBw/Ti60 composites is increased by 61.1%, 57.4% and 45.5% compared with that of the monolithic

Ti60 alloy at 600°C, 700°C and 800°C, respectively.

- (3) The superior improvement of tensile properties at high temperatures can be mainly attributed to the network microstructure, grain refinement, TiB whiskers and usage of large spherical Ti60 powders.

Acknowledgements

This work is financially supported by the National Natural Science Foundation of China (NSFC) under Grant Nos.51101042, 51271064 and 51228102, the 5th-class Special Foundation (2012T50327) and the 50th-class General Foundation (2011M500653) from the China Postdoctoral Science Foundation.

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